

THE CHEMISTRY OF HEALING: *HETEROATOMIC DERIVATIZATION AND THEIR MEDICINAL APPLICATIONS*

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ABSTRACT

Heterocyclic compounds are gaining attention for their medical and biological applications, with over 90% of new drugs containing them. Among all the heterocyclic molecules, mimics of nitrogen-based heterocycles occupy an exclusive position as a valuable source of therapeutic agents in medicinal chemistry. More than 75% of drugs approved by the FDA and currently available in the market are nitrogen-containing heterocyclic moieties. In the forthcoming decade, a much greater share of new nitrogen-based pharmaceuticals is anticipated. Many new nitrogen-based heterocycles have been designed. The number of novel *N*-heterocyclic moieties with significant physiological properties and promising applications in medicinal chemistry is ever-growing. In the present investigation, we amalgamate isatin and several aromatic aldehydes to produce a few thiazolidinone derivatives. This synthesis aims to contribute to the ongoing progress in the development of innovative nitrogen-containing heterocycles.

Keywords: Black pepper, chemical composition, biological activities.

INTRODUCTION

Heteroatomic/cyclic compounds are a group of cyclic organic compounds that contain at least one atom other than carbon in their ring structure [1]. Heterocyclic organic chemistry is the branch of organic chemistry dealing with the synthesis, properties, and applications of organic heterocycles [2]. It is found that over 50% of identified compounds are heterocycles [3] and nitrogen heterocycles are present in 59% of drugs approved by the US FDA [4]. The most found heteroatoms in these compounds are nitrogen, oxygen, and sulfur. Heterocyclic compounds are abundant in both plants and animal products, and they make up a significant portion of natural organic compounds. They are found in various important substances such as alkaloids, natural dyes, drugs, proteins, and enzymes. These compounds can be classified based on their electronic structure, primarily as saturated and unsaturated. Saturated heterocyclic compounds exhibit similar properties to their acyclic counterparts but with modified steric properties. Examples of saturated

heterocyclic compounds include piperidine and tetrahydrofuran. On the other hand, unsaturated heterocyclic compounds with 5- and 6-member rings have been extensively studied due to their unstrained nature. This category includes compounds like epoxides, thiadiazoles, triazoles, oxadiazole, tetrazoles, pyridine, thiophene, pyrrole, furan etc. Some important examples of benzo-fused heterocycles are quinoline, isoquinoline, indole, morpholine, piperazine, benzothiophene, and benzofuran etc. [Figure-1]. The advancement of various organic synthesis methods has significantly contributed to the field of chemical sciences [5-9]. *N*-heterocyclic compounds, which are widely found in nature, play a crucial role in the development of biologically important molecules such as vitamins, nucleic acids, pharmaceuticals, antibiotics, and agrochemicals [10-14]. These compounds are also essential components of pharmacologically active molecules, including the base pairs of DNA and RNA. With their unique properties and diverse applications, nitrogen-containing heterocyclic molecules have

become increasingly important in the fields of organic and medicinal chemistry, as well as in the pharmaceutical industry [15-17]. Pharmaceutical active ingredients frequently contain heterocyclic structures and are commonly sold as medications [Figure-2, 3]. Numerous nitrogen-containing heterocyclic compounds have been identified to demonstrate various pharmacological effects including anticancer, anti-HIV, antimalarial, anti-tubercular, antimicrobial, and diabetic activities [18-24]. The significance of nitrogen

heterocycles in drug design is evident from the 97,400 plus publications on nitrogen heterocycles published between 2009 and early 2020 [Figure-4]. As per the literature review earlier, here we opted to utilize substituted isatin and aromatic aldehydes to produce substituted Schiff's bases. These were then reacted with thioglycolic acid in the presence of anhydrous zinc chloride to produce the desired substituted thiazolidinone mimics.

Figure-2

Figure-4

β -Lactams

The β -lactam ring, a four-membered cyclic amide ring system, commonly called “ β -lactam ring” or “azetidinone”, is highly valued in the design of antibiotics and organic synthesis. It plays a crucial role in the bioactivity profile of antibiotics and serves as a versatile building block for the synthesis of various bioactive heterocycles [25-29]. In addition to its role in antibiotics, β -lactams have other clinical applications such as β -lactamase inhibitors and cholesterol absorption inhibitor [30-31]. The wide range of applications has sparked interest in further developing the β -lactam ring, leading to the creation of various protocols for synthesizing four-membered ring β -lactams [32-33]. The emergence of bacterial resistance to existing β -lactam antibiotics has further fueled

research in this field [Figure-5]. No cytotoxic effects were observed in the in vitro cytotoxic studies conducted on NIH-3T3 cell lines, even at concentrations higher than those demonstrated to possess antibiotic activity by Rosa et al. [34]. Similarly, Vigliotta et al. [35] devised a strategy to create a hybrid structure by merging a lactam ring with a cephalosporin moiety using chains of different lengths ($n = 1$ to 7). The synthesized compounds were then evaluated against specific strains of Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, demonstrating their efficacy against Gram-positive bacteria. Notably, the compounds with longer carbon chains exhibited superior antibacterial activity compared to the reference drug. Furthermore, all the compounds exhibited no cytotoxicity on tested MRC-5 and Calu-1 cell lines at the active antimicrobial doses. Pagadala et al. [36] synthesized bicyclic ring

structures with monocyclic 2-azetidinone rings connected by spacers of varying lengths and flexibility. These compounds were tested in vitro for antibacterial activity against *B. subtilis*, *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *K. pneumoniae*. Results showed that all compounds had

moderate to good activity, comparable to standard drugs. Notably, compounds with a methoxy-, nitro-, or amino-group on the phenyl ring at the C-4 position of the azetidinone ring exhibited the highest activity.

Triazoles

The 1,2,3-triazole moiety serves as a crucial pharmacophore system in nitrogen-based molecules and is a fundamental building block in the exploration of novel biological targets. These heterocyclic motifs, consisting of three nitrogen heteroatoms, can be easily synthesized through the application of 'click' chemistry, specifically copper-catalyzed azide-alkyne cycloaddition [Cu-AAC] reactions. Generally, 1,2,3-triazoles possess a stable 'linker' property that resists hydrolysis under both acidic and basic conditions, as

well as metabolic degradation. These compounds exhibit interactions with diverse biological targets through hydrogen bonding, noncovalent interactions, van der Waals forces, and dipole-dipole bonding interactions. Additionally, triazoles display weak acidic and weak basic characteristics, making them more susceptible to reducing agents. Notably, the 1,2,3-triazole-based compound known as carboxyamidotriazole has undergone successful clinical evaluation for cancer treatment [37-39] (Figure-6).

Meltem et al. [40] developedazole-functionalized fluoroquinolone hybrids and tested their antibacterial and antioxidant properties. Some of the fourteen hybrids exhibited stronger antibacterial effects against test microorganisms compared to ampicillin, with MIC values ranging from 0.03 to 0.25 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. The study conducted by Bektaş et al. [41] focused on the synthesis and antimicrobial properties of novel 1,2,4-triazole derivatives. The results indicated that compounds 3 and 8 displayed moderate antimicrobial effects against *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, while compounds 11 and 12 exhibited moderate activities towards *Enterobacter aerogenes*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterococcus faecalis*, and *Bacillus cereus*. Compounds 13 and 14 demonstrated good

antimicrobial activities against the tested microorganisms, and Mannich bases 15a,b showed either good or moderate antimicrobial effects. However, none of the synthesized compounds showed antimicrobial activity against *Candida tropicalis* and *Candida albicans*.

Imidazoles and Benzoimidazoles

The significant structural characteristics of the five-membered imidazole and benzoimidazole moieties set them apart as crucial heterocycles, and these formations are present in numerous natural products and synthetic compounds. The imidazole-based derivatives, known for their electron-rich nature, are valuable in their ability to readily bind with various receptors and

enzymes in the biological profile, thereby displaying a wide range of biological activities [42-43]. Several imidazole-based molecules (such as oxiconazole, dacarbazine, and clotrimazole) that exhibit potent antifungal and anticancer properties are currently utilized as drugs in clinical settings (Figure 16). The field of medicinal chemistry is witnessing a rapid expansion in the realm of imidazole and benzoimidazole possessed molecules [Figure-7]. El-Feky and colleagues [44] synthesized and tested various new quinoline derivatives to evaluate their anti-inflammatory and ulcerogenic properties. They conducted a docking study on the COX-2 binding pocket to assess the selectivity of these compounds against the COX-2 enzyme. The most potent compounds (5a, 8a, and 11a) exhibited superior activity compared to celecoxib. Compound 11a displayed the highest anti-inflammatory effects and showed the best binding affinity to the COX-2 binding site. Additionally, compounds 9c, 9e, 10a, and 11a did not exhibit any ulcerogenic activity. Yanhui et al. [45]

conducted a study on the antibacterial and anti-biofilm effects of certain compounds on *S. aureus*. They found that ionic liquids containing imidazole chloride and alkyl chains of twelve and sixteen carbons exhibited varying levels of antibacterial effectiveness, with the effectiveness improving as the alkyl chain length increased. The researchers also investigated the impact of C_nMIMCl ILs on *S. aureus*, and observed that toxicity increased as the length of the imidazolidiny side chains increased. Among the ILs studied, $C_{12}MIMCl$ was selected for further analysis due to its ability to induce internal and external changes in *S. aureus*, ultimately leading to bacterial death. The researchers discovered that high levels of reactive oxygen species (ROS) caused oxidative stress, disrupted metabolism, and resulted in cell death. Additionally, damage to the cell membrane led to leakage and fragmentation. In vivo tests conducted on mice confirmed the antibacterial properties of the ILs against skin blisters.

Figure-7

Pyrazoles

Pyrazole is a renowned heterocycle composed of five nitrogen-containing members, known for its diverse applications in both synthetic and biological contexts. Several drugs derived from pyrazole, including celecoxib, rimonabant, difenamilole, and fezolamine, have been developed with exceptional anti-inflammatory, anti-obesity, analgesic, and/or antidepressant effects. These drugs are employed in the management of various diseases (Figure 23) [46-49]. Akbas and colleagues [50] conducted the synthesis of a range of 1H-pyrazole-3-carboxylic acid derivatives and

assessed their antibacterial properties against *Bacillus cereus*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Pseudomonas putida*. The findings indicated that compound 151 stood out as the most effective compound in the series, demonstrating antibacterial efficacy against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria. Xiong et al. [51] reported synthesis, and biological evaluation of novel thiazolyl substituted bis-pyrazole oxime derivatives with potent antitumor activities by selectively inducing apoptosis and ROS in cancer Cells.

Figure-8

Quinolines

The quinoline moiety is a well-known entity and is a ubiquitous alkaloid subunit of many natural products. Quinoline is an important pharmacophore moiety as it has been described to possess various biological activities, which include antimalarial, antibiotic, antitubercular, antiproliferative, antiprotozoal, antihypertensive, anti-HIV properties [52-54] and

many are commercially available in market [Figure-9]. Raynes et al. [55] are found to possess a good degree of antimalarial activity against both chloroquine-resistant and chloroquine-sensitive parasites. While 7-chloroquinolinyl thioureas synthesized by Mahajan et al. [56] and claimed their potential antimalarial potential.

Figure-9

Quinazolines

Quinazolines are nitrogen-containing six-membered heterocyclic compounds that contain a benzene ring system fused to a pyrimidine at two adjacent carbon atoms. Quinazolines and their analogs possess a wide

range of biological activities. Many quinazoline compounds were reported as growth factor receptor (EGFR) tyrosine kinase inhibitors, such as gefitinib, erlotinib, lapatinib and afatinib (Figure-10) [57].

Figure-10

Pyrimidines and pyrimidinones

Derivatives of pyrimidines and pyrimidinone derivatives are highly regarded in organic synthesis due to their diverse biological activities. The pyrimidine nucleus is composed of a six-membered 1,3-diazine ring with a ketone group. These analogs play a crucial role in various biologically active compounds, including natural products and nucleic acids. Additionally, this type of heterocyclic compound is

utilized in medicinal chemistry for its therapeutic applications, serving as a fundamental component in numerous drug candidates and nucleic acids, sharing a structural similarity with purines [57]. Recently, the US FDA has approved several pyrimidines and pyrimidinone derivatives (ibrutinib, capecitabine, folinic acid, and monastrol) as anticancer agents [Figure-11].

Figure-11

Designing and synthesis

In the current study, we selected aromatic aldehydes, indole-2,3-diones, thioglycolic acid to yield targeted heterocyclic moieties as depicted in scheme-1.

Scheme-1

3-Thiosemicarbazido indole-2-one [1]: A mixture of indole-2,3-dione (2 g), semicarbazide (1.23 g) in methanol (50 mL) was refluxed for 1 hr. The completion of reaction was checked by TLC and excess of methanol distilled out. The cooled, refluxed residual was poured into ice water, filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallized from methanol to obtain compound **1** (80%), m.p. 200 °C; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 1200, 1610, 1682, 1710, 3144, 3419; ^1H NMR ($\text{CDCl}_3+\text{DMSO}-d_6$): 6.75-6.95 (d, 1H_d), 7.02-7.10 (t, 1H_c), 7.22-7.30 (t, 1H_b), 7.5707.62 (d, 1H_a), 8.90 (bs, 2H), 9.36 (bs, 1H) ppm. Anal. Calcd for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_8\text{N}_4\text{SO}$: C, 49.09; H, 3.63; N, 25.45. Found: C, 49.38; H, 3.41; N, 25.60%. MS: $[\text{M}]^+$ at m/z 220.

2-Amino-1,3,4-oxadiazino(6,5-b) indole [2]: Compound **1** (3 g) mixed with small quantity of cold, concentrate sulfuric acid (1.52 mmole) and left at room temp for 16 hr. After this, reaction mixture was poured into ice-cold water, neutralized with liquid ammonia to obtain solid mass, which was filtered, washed with water, dried, and recrystallized from methanol to yield compound **2** (60%), m.p. 340 °C; IR(KBr, Cm^{-1}): 1295, 1611, 1683, 3144, 3420; ^1H NMR ($\text{CDCl}_3+\text{DMSO}-d_6$): 6.89-6.97 (d, 1H_d), 7.00-7.05 (t, 1H_c), 7.26-7.31 (t, 1H_b), 7.56-7.59 (d, 1H_a), 8.58 (bs, 2H) ppm. Anal. Calcd for $\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{N}_4\text{S}$: C, 53.46; H, 2.97; N, 27.72. Found: C, 53.26; H, 3.15; N, 27.94%. MS: $[\text{M}]^+$ at m/z 202.

General procedure of arylidenamino-1,3,4-oxadiazino[6,5-b]indole [3-4]: The equimolar

mixture (0.01 mole) of compound **2** and an aromatic aldehydes (0.01 mole) in ethanol was refluxed for 6 hr in presence of glacial acetic acid. The completion of reaction was checked by TLC and excess of methanol distilled off. After this, refluxed reaction mixture was poured into ice-water, filtered, washed with water, and dried. Dried mass was recrystallized from ethanol to yield compound **3-4**.

Benzylidenamino-1,3,4-oxadiazino[6,5-b]indole

[3]: m.p. 188°C; IR (KBr, Cm^{-1}) 1296, 1611, 1682, 31; ^1H NMR ($\text{CDCl}_3+\text{DMSO}-d_6$): 6.47-6.68 (m, 5H), 6.86-6.96 (d, 1H_d), 7.02-7.12 (t, 1H_c), 7.23-7.28 (t, 1H), 7.56-7.60 (d, 1H), 8.29 (s, 1H) ppm. Anal. Calcd for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{O}$: C, 66.20; H, 3.44; N, 19.31. Found: C, 65.96; H, 3.61; N, 19.18%. MS: $[\text{M}]^+$ at m/z 274.

2-[4-Chlorobenzylidenamino]-1, 3, 4-oxadiazino[6,5-b]indole 4: m.p. 222°C (methanol-water); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 673, 1062, 1297, 1612, 1680, 3145, 3420; ^1H NMR ($\text{CDCl}_3+\text{DMSO}-d_6$): 3.72 (s, 3H), 6.72 (s, 1H), 6.90-6.92 (d, 1H), 7.01-7.06 (t, 1H), 7.27-7.32 (t, 1H), 7.76-7.79 (d, 1H), 7.87-7.90 (d, 1H). Anal. Calcd for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_9\text{N}_4\text{OCl}$: C, 60.71; H, 3.57; N, 16.66. Found: C, 60.50; H, 3.32; N, 16.39%. MS: $[\text{M}]$ at m/z 308.5.

General procedure of 2-Aryl-4-thiazolidinon-3-yl-1,3,4-oxadiazino[6,5-b]indole [5-6]:

An ethanolic mixture of derivatives **3** & **4** refluxed for 5-7 hrs in presence of glacial acetic acid. On

completion, excess of solvent distilled and residue poured in ice-water to yield residues [5-6].

2-Phenyl-4-thiazolidinon-3-yl]-1,3,4-oxadiazino[6,5-*b*]indole [5]: m.p. 188 °C (acetic acid-water); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 1055, 1300, 1605, 1697, 3200, 3466; $^1\text{H NMR}$ ($\text{CDCl}_3+\text{DMSO}-d_6$): 3.70 (s, 2H), 6.56-6.97 (m, 5H), 7.25 (s, 1H,N-CH-), 7.56-8.17 (m, 4H). Anal. Calcd for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S}$: C, 62.06; H, 3.44; N, 16.09. Found: C, 61.89; H, 3.31; N, 16.12%. MS: [M] at m/z 348.

2-[4-Chlorophenyl-4-thiazolidinon-3-yl]-1,3,4-oxadiazino[6,5-*b*]indole [6]: m.p. 209 °C (acetic acid-water); IR (KBr, cm^{-1}): 1055, 1300, 1605, 1697, 3200, 3466; $^1\text{H NMR}$ ($\text{CDCl}_3+\text{DMSO}-d_6$): 3.61 (s, 2H), 6.46-6.88 (m, 4H), 7.25 (s, 1H,N-CH-), 7.56-8.17 (m, 4H). Anal. Calcd for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{S}\text{Cl}$: C, 56.47; H, 2.87; N, 14.64. Found: C, 56.70; H, 2.80; N, 14.60%. MS: [M] at m/z 382.5.

Conclusion

The field of nitrogen-based compounds in medicine is expanding daily, and their various analogs offer a viable and important avenue for the discovery of drugs with diverse biological applications. N-heterocyclic frameworks provide a high level of structural diversity, which has proven to be valuable in the search for new therapeutic agents that can improve pharmacokinetics and other physicochemical features. Many drugs currently in clinical use have severe side effects and have developed resistance to multiple drugs. Despite this, they have been extensively utilized to treat various diseases due to their high therapeutic potency. The research and development of nitrogen-based compounds in medicinal chemistry is a rapidly growing and increasingly active area of study. Significant progress has been made in the field of N-heterocyclic skeleton medicinal chemistry. The numerous advantages of nitrogen-containing drugs in the field of medicine, such as easy preparation, low toxicity, minimal adverse effects, high bioavailability, reduced drug resistance, and good biocompatibility, provide strong motivation for further research and development. Therefore, understanding the properties of these scaffolds is crucial in the current drug discovery and design system. In this review, we have extensively covered the current trends in families of nitrogen-based heterocyclic molecules, including β -lactam, pyrazole, imidazole, 1,2,4-triazole, pyrimidine, quinoline, and quinazoline derivatives.

These molecules exhibit highly promising biological properties, such as anticancer, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, antifungal, antitubercular, antidiabetic, antioxidant, anti-HIV, and other medicinal properties.

Statement of Declaration

This work is part of the dissertation works of M.Sc. final semester students Aman Deep and Prachi.

Conflicts of interest

The author states there are no conflicts of interest

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